

**Learning
Technology
Accelerator**

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR

LEA

**D 5.1 Capacity Building Seminar Report
30.9.2018**

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1. CAPACITY BUILDING SEMINAR

In the framework of the LEA project, Capacity Building seminars are to be organized connected to each major milestone of the PPI and PCP process. Thus, according to the initial planning, a seminar has been organized to clarify the pre-requisites and key steps to design and implement an innovation procurement process.

This seminar was an internal Capacity Building seminar to increase the LEA partners, particularly about PPI as an innovation procurement instrument. The seminar was only intended to the consortium members serving as a pilot to the external Capacity Building seminars coming later in the LEA project. According to the Description of Work of the LEA Project, these external seminars will take place between M8 and M14 of the project implementation.

Internal Capacity Building on PCP and PPI

Venue: Halmstad

Date: 18th and 19th June 2018

1.1 Brief Description

The seminar addressed the consortium members with the focus of promoting PPI and sharing of knowledge and tools, as well as served as a starting point to enable the group of procurers and all other partners on the preparation of prepare a procurement call using PPI approach, which is based on IMAILE PCP results and achievements.

From the knowledge gained, it is also expected that all partners, including the non-procurers, acquire the necessary competences and capacity to spread the word, attracting and engaging other players to the LEARNTECH Accelerator Eco System.

These outputs achieved from the event will also serve as a proper basis for the future Capacity Building events which are planned by the consortium where it is expected to address other procurers outside the consortium.

The Capacity Building seminar is important for the decision makers and the procurement officers involved in the procurement process since they are responsible the planning and execution of the procurement and related activities (e.g. to conduct of market consultations, definition of technical specifications, preparation of tender documentation, evaluation of tenders and selection of successful bidders, as well as management and monitoring of the procurement contract(s)).

The LEA's case public procurement on innovation will be focused on education, specifically on Personalized Learning Environment solutions.

1.2 Objectives

The aim of the first CBS was to explore and explain:

- What form of innovation procurement a public procurer could choose – Understanding PPI;

- What are the main steps that public procurers should consider when preparing and implementing an innovation procurement procedure;
- Why each of these steps is important;
- How to implement each of these steps;
- How to prepare joint procurements.

Capacity Building seminar outlined the step-by-step approach in order to implement a PPI procurement.

The seminar was based on the applicable legal framework, reviewed literature, policy documents and lessons learned from innovation procurements (PCP and PPI) already implemented at both EU and national level.

2. METHODOLOGY

In order to understand what were the main and more urgent needs to be addressed under the form of presentations at this first internal Capacity Building seminar, a voting was made by all the consortium members during the kick-off meeting. They voted on a list of 13 needs, classifying them as (1-very important to learn about; 2-important to learn about; 3-not so important I already know about it.)

The topics presented at the seminar were the most voted ones.

After the CBS an online questionnaire was sent online to all the participants to evaluate their satisfaction and to understand what could be improved to the future CBS, which the results are presented at section 4 of this document.

Table 1: Internal Capacity Building Agenda

Monday 18th June

Time	Topic	Responsible parties
13:30 – 13:45	Introduction	Inova+
13:45 – 14:30	Understanding Innovation Procurement - Instruments and definitions	Sara Bedin, EUPK
14:30 – 15:00	Steps for PPI preparation - Short presentation of Success business cases	INOVA+ & Sara Bedin
15:00 – 15:45	Steps for PPI preparation - Open Market consultation	EUPK, Sara Bedin
15:45-16:00	Coffee break	
16:00 – 18:00	Steps for PPI preparation – Needs assessment and description workshop	Oulu – Inova+, Sara Bedin & JYU assisting

Tuesday 19th June

Time	Topic	Responsible parties
09:00 – 09:15	Catch-up from the day before	INOVA+ & Sara Bedin
09:15 – 09:45	Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link	Mr Tsanidis, EC
09:45 – 10:30	Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement	Mr Tsanidis, EC

	actions	
10:30– 11:15	Steps for PPI preparation – How to define awarding criteria	INOVA +
11:15 – 11:30	Coffee break	
11:30 – 12:30	Steps for PPI preparation - Procurers' roundtable	Oulu – Inova+, Sara Bedin and JYU will assist
12:30– 13:00	Q&A	All
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch	

3. PPI CAPACITY BUILDING SEMINAR CONTENT OVERVIEW

In this chapter, we present the CBS contents from the various sessions in the seminar.

3.1 Understanding Innovation Procurement - Instruments and definitions

The following content was presented:

- The PCP and PPI separation and its complementarity, and the integration of the innovation partnership (IP);
- The Legal framework: PCP, PPI and IP;
- The main differences between PCP/PPI and IP;
- The common characteristics of PCP and PPI and its key properties;
- Innovation driven procurement procedures: common elements;
- The innovation procurement: need analysis and description;

- The TLC-PE method and the FAST methodology;
- Innovation procurement: Use cases.

Methods and techniques:

TLC-PE¹: an innovation life-cycle cost method that takes into account the cost and benefits of the innovative solution over the entire life cycle of the innovative solution.

The method TLC-PE (Total Life-Cycle - functional and PErformance description) creates associations between expected functionalities and quantified performance targets. It classifies functionalities and related performances along the solution lifecycle phases (production, delivery, installation, use, management, maintenance and disposal) in order to encourage suppliers to propose solutions with higher long-term performance and lower (total life-cycle) costs.

FAST methodology: One methodology used to elicit the functional specifications is called FAST (Functional Analysis System Technique). According to this methodology, the basic element of a system is the Function that describes the original intent or purpose that a product, process or service expected to be performed.

The description of a Function is restricted to a two words format:

Active Verb + (Measurable) Name.

The Verb is used to answer to the question: What does it do?

While the Name is used to answer to the question: What does the Verb apply to?

Brief summary:

¹ Sara Bedin, 2012, proprietary methodology

- Innovation Partnerships should be used only for the purchase of specialized/unique product/service;
- The only separation between the R&D and the purchase/deployment stages (PCP/PPI) is preventing the distortion of competition, reason why PCP/PPI are state aid free (if implemented according to COM(2007) 799/ EU Procurement Directives respectively);
- PCP and PPI have in common the objective and the price/quality solution that better fit public sector needs;
- PCP and PPI key properties: Identification and assessment of unmet needs within the public bodies; Involvement of users in specification of requirements and/or during the design process and/or piloting; SoA analysis via open market consultations and early market engagement to select between “developmental” and “adaptive” procurement; Specification of functional / performance-based requirements; Verification of innovative solutions (either within the tendering process or in pre-commercial phase); Allocation of risks and benefit (including IPR); Enable the participation of emerging players and SMEs.

Due to the interest demonstrated in the presentation ***Understanding Innovation Procurement - Instruments and definitions***, the time of this session were extended for 45 minutes more. It was decided, between the CBS participants, not to present the ***Steps for PPI preparation – Short presentation of success business cases*** and ***Steps for PPI preparation – How to define awarding criteria***. These sessions will be later presented and available in the form of webinars.

3.2 Steps for PPI preparation - Open Market consultation

The following content was presented:

- OMC PPI preparations and timeline;
- Definition of OMC;
- The “How to” guidelines;
- The 4 A concept;
- The Supplier Information Package (SIP);
- The how and why: what to ask the market players.

Brief summary:

- OMC is a Powerful instrument that helps to understand the gap between the demand and supply sides with a twofold purpose: 1 - Gathering information from the market suppliers; 2- Informing the market about the procurement plans (and the needs of public authorities);
- There are steps to be followed to the open market consultation:
 - Identify tasks, responsibilities and time plan;
 - A communication plan, SIP and transparent Q&A management;
 - Plan a transparent documentation process incl. collection of feedback, use of the RFI data (input to PPI assessment criteria);
 - Identify and plan the relevant events – “Go-to-meet-the-market” approach;
 - Publish a Prior Information Notice (PIN) in the Official Journal of the European Union, on the project website and other suitable dissemination channels (min. 1 month in advance);
 - Request for information in stages – RFI I and RFI II;
 - Take into consideration legal aspect: Public Procurement Directive 2014/24/EU; Parity and transparency – pre-selection of market operators for the procurement phase is not allowed; Protection of supplier's IPR.

- We must follow the 4 A concept for a good OMC:
 - ALERT the market about the upcoming PPI;
 - ATTRACT suppliers to respond to the call by the market the project;
 - ASK -Request for information (RFI) – workshop & webinar;
 - ANNOUNCE the call.

- The Supplies information package must answer the Why (Initial challenges and needs), How much (PPI Contract value), Who (Procurement size (long-term market, first customers)), Who and Where (Timetable and events where to meet and interact) and How to participate (Surveys and RFI).

3.3 Steps for PPI preparation – Needs assessment and description workshop

Oulu, represented by Markku Lang and Jari presented:

The PPI preparation – balancing our needs:

- The Results of allorideas- questionnaire. What can be learned from PCP process in IMAILE project?
- Current challenges & Future perspectives - Scoping to 2030;
- Dreams for LEA? What motivates me?
- Learning Scenarios from IMAILE, what's relevant, what should be replaced?;
- Mapping the New Learning Scenario;
- Participatory round tour.

Brief summary:

- On the questionnaire, the results showed that the features of PLE were more important for the partners. The most voted one were:
 - Support all students to reach their goals in a personalized way (1st place);
 - The use of creative and collaborative learning methods in a personalized way;
 - Reduce the numbers of early dropouts.
- The current challenges on education must address the two skills that are truly recognized as the 21st century' skills: information literacy and information management.
- The challenges faced in implementing technology in classrooms and recommendations:
 - For learners: Large learning gap among learners in the classroom: making classroom curriculum difficult to fulfil and cater to each individual learner's learning needs. => Increasing interest of learners in gaining new knowledge;
 - For teachers/educators: The burden of learning and using technology usually lies on the teachers => Proper training and support has to be available and provided to (in-service /pre-service) teachers;
 - For schools: Teacher-centred model with exploring methods of implementing and utilizing technology in the classroom => Working towards a Towards school-centred ICT integration model;
 - For parents: Because parents themselves experienced learning via the conventional method, and hence, they do not believe that by bringing technology into the classroom would help their children in learning => Need to increase awareness on the benefits of technology;
 - For developers: Complicated system designs which require;

- User's customization = interest is easily lost => More attention should be made on the USE OF TECHNOLOGY instead of the technology itself; Too much pedagogical elements clearly visible =" ah, this-this teaching system".
- Future perspectives for PLE, towards a "smart learning environment" could involve technologies like METATUTOR, ASTUDY, SLAM, Educational Robot.

Workshop – Part I

The second part of the presentation was a hands-on workshop, where the participants were divided into 7 groups, led by each one of the 7 procurers (Halmstad, Konnevesi, Madeburg, Goteborg, Viladecans, Torino and CMBraga). The groups worked together, having as a starting point several learning scenarios from IMAILE, where the main objective was to think of "what's relevant and what should be replaced on these learning scenarios".

The workshop was based on a Learning Scenario which is a tool to visualize and tell a story of needs and wanted workflow in the near future in schools. It also tells a story about the school culture we want.

The second part of the workshop was continued with the session 1.4.6 Steps for PPI preparation - Procurers' roundtable.

3.4 Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link

Vasileios Tsanidis presented:

- Main features and framework of public procurement of innovative solutions (PPI)
- The INNOVATION PARTNERSHIPS VS PCP/PPI

Vasileios Tsanidis
European Commission
DG CNECT
Digital Single Market
Start-Ups and Innovation Unit (F3)

Lessons learnt:

- PCP/PPI: the Legal separation between R&D and purchase /deployment of the innovative solution;
- Innovation Partnerships – a combination of R&D and purchase/deployment of the innovative solution in one procedure;
- PPI cannot be implemented through Innovation Partnerships.

3.5 Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement actions

Vasileios Tsanidis presented:

- The Joint procurement vs coordinated procurement: the EU Procurement directives;
- H2020 requirements.

Brief summary:

The provisions of centralised purchasing activities by a central purchasing body located in another Member State shall be conducted in accordance with the national provisions of the Member State where the central purchasing body is located.

- The contract award can be centralised or distributed:
 - In case of 1 Joint procurement either one lead procurer awarding all contracts to all suppliers on behalf of all procurers in the buyer's group; Or one lead procurer only awarding a framework contract with lots to each supplier (e.g. lot per procurer), and each procurer awarding (a) specific contract(s) for his lot(s) to the supplier(s) delivering the solution(s) he buys.
 - In case of several separate but coordinated procurements, each procurer awarding his own contract(s) directly himself.
- In case of a PPI after a PCP according to the conditions described, the negotiated procedure without Publication foreseen in the EU public procurement directives can then be used. At least three offers must be asked including from the R&D providers that successfully completed the pre-ceding PCP.

3.6 Steps for PPI preparation - Procurers' roundtable

Oulu, represented by Markku Lang presented:

PPI preparation – viewing scenarios and balancing our needs:

- Co-writing the new learning scenario;
- Showtime;
- PPI preparation - Procurers' roundtable + Q&A.

Workshop – part II

On the second part of the needs assessment workshop, the learning scenarios previously analysed by the initial group were analysed by all the other groups. Only the 1 member from the initial group stayed at the table with the scenario and explained to other members the changes that were

being purposed by all the others. In the end, the idea was to have all the scenarios analysed and commented by all the participants.

4. RESULTS FROM THE CBS SATISFACTION EVALUATION SURVEY

The Consortia members within the framework of the 1st CBS have learned about:

- Understanding Innovation Procurement - Instruments and definitions
- Steps for PPI preparation - Open Market consultation
- Steps for PPI preparation – Needs assessment and description workshop
- Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link
- Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement actions

Taking into consideration that this seminar was an internal seminar, with the purpose of acting as a pilot for future external Capacity building seminars, a Satisfaction Evaluation Survey was delivered to all the participant by email on the end of the CBS. At the CBS 29 persons attended, and 66% answered the questionnaire, but we were able to cover all the 17 of LEA'S partners.

The questions and the results are presented below:

1. How satisfied were you with the CBS? (1 – completely unsatisfied; 2 – unsatisfied; 3 – satisfied; 4 – very satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied)

- The “Procurers” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.11.
- The “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.67.
- The “Networks” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.00.
- The “Learning Technology Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.75.
- The lowest evaluation (3) was from the “Procurers” (1).
- The highest evaluation (5) was from the “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” (3)

2. Which topics of the CBS did you find more interesting or useful?

- The “Procurers” have preferences on “Understanding Innovation Procurement – Instruments and definitions” (4), followed by “Understanding the legal framework – How to manage the PCP-PPI link” (2), “Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement action” (1), “Steps for PPI preparation – Needs assessment and description workshop” (1) and “Steps for PPI preparation – Procurers’ roundtable”(1).
- The “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” have preferences on “Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement action” (3) followed by “Understanding the legal framework – How to manage the PCP-PPI link” (1)”.
- The “Networks” have equal preferences on “Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement action” (1), “Understanding the legal framework – How to manage the PCP-PPI link” (1) and “Steps for PPI preparation – Needs assessment and description workshop” (1).
- The “Learning Technology Experts” have preferences on “Understanding Innovation Procurement – Instruments and definitions” (2) followed by

“Understanding the legal framework – Coordinated versus Joint procurement action” (1).

3. How satisfied were you with the practical activities during the CBS?

(1 – completely unsatisfied; 2 – unsatisfied; 3 – satisfied; 4 – very satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied)

- The “Procurers” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 3.44.
- The “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 5.00.
- The “Networks” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 3.67.
- The “Learning Technology Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.67.
- The lowest evaluations (3) were from the “Procurers” (5) followed by “Learning Technology Experts”.
- The highest evaluations (5) were from “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” (4) followed by “Learning Technology Experts” (2).

4. How satisfied were you with the trainers? (1 – completely unsatisfied; 2 – unsatisfied; 3 – satisfied; 4 – very satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied)

- The “Procurers” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 3.89.
- The “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.75.
- The “Networks” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.33.
- The “Learning Technology Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.00.
- The lowest evaluation (2) was from the “Learning Technology Experts” (1).
- The highest evaluation (5) was from the “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” (5).

5. Please comment on the organisation of the CBS, considering the venue, duration and meals (1 – completely unsatisfied; 2 – unsatisfied; 3 – satisfied; 4 – very satisfied; 5 – completely satisfied).

- The “Procurers” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 3.89.
- The “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 5.00.
- The “Networks” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 4.00.
- The “Learning Technology Experts” evaluated the satisfaction with an average of 5.00.
- The lowest evaluation (2) was from the “Procurers” (1).
- The highest evaluation (5) was from “Legal, PCP/PPI Dissemination Experts” (4) followed by “and “Learning Technology Experts” (3).

6. Which other PCP and PPI themes would like to be presented on the following CBS (also including webinars)?

The themes included in this voting, resulted from the aggregation of the topics listed on the first voting that occurred at the kick-off meeting in Brussels and the themes that were not presented at the CBS.

The questionnaire also included the following open questions, that we summarize on the conclusions section:

- Question 3 - Please provide comments on the topics that you have found more relevant or interesting.
- Question 4 - Please provide comments on the topics that you have found less interesting or relevant.
- Question 7 - How do you think the CBC could have been made more effective?

Question 10 - Comments and suggestions (including activities or initiatives you think would be useful, for the future).

5. Conclusions and guidelines for future CBS

This questionnaire was used, not only a for purpose of evaluating the overall satisfaction of the participants, but also to understand what could be improved for the next external CBS sessions. For that reason, on the questionnaire, 4 open questions were inserted for the respondent to provide their comments and suggestion. Based on their suggestions we were able to build a few guidelines that Will help us on the future CBS:

Guidelines for future CBS

- Try to simplify. PCP and PPI are not easy to understand, so presentation must try to focus on the main topics in an easy common language, using visual graphics and examples whenever possible;
- PCP and PPI must be presented following a step by step methodology, from the preparation until the execution;
- Having external experts is crucial, to reinforce the knowledge and having external opinions is always a plus;

Guidelines for future CBS

- Always try to have some previous experiences from other Project son PCP and PPI, to collect lessons learnt;
- Save some time at the end of the presentations for Questions and Answers – participation is very welcome and benefits the both sides;
- Try to have shorter presentation covering more thematic, to give the public a general overview of the all process;
- Take into consideration the levels of knowledge that the public might have on the PCP and PPI topics;
- Try, whenever possible to have the presentations available or to be assisted online, for the ones who cannot be physically present.

The main conclusion was that in general, the participant w very satisfied with the CBS, regarding the presentation, the trainers, as well as the venue. The consortium considered that the surveys were very useful to know in what ways the contents could be improved for the following external CBS. During the seminar it was perceived that there are clearly different background and levels of knowledge between the 4 groups of partners, being the Procurers, the group where a more urgent need of knowledge on PPI was identified.

The participants acknowledged that although every PPI project has differences from the PCP and – besides, the legal framework - there is no

clear-cut way for the implementation. Therefore, the methodologies and experiences of other organizations will be a great added value for the LEA project and need to be incorporated in the agenda of the coming CBSs.

Key message 1: The innovation procurement and the procurers must be well prepared. If there are different levels of knowledge, the seminars must be adequate and prepared to answer all of them, trying to make the effort of leveraging the ones that know less about PCP and PPI, and knowing that this is always a continuous learning process until the end of the project.

Key message 2: Every consortium must capitalize their internal expertise. Nevertheless, if there is a lack of expertise, external experts must invite to pass along their experience and knowledge.

Key message 3: Investing into innovation procurement is not only challenging, but also requires a lot of preparation and time. Some tasks might look like extremely time consuming and requires extra resources, however this is the price of being a pioneer in the field of innovation procurement on education.

Based on the feedback from LEA internal capacity building seminar, in addition to the topics covered by the session, the following aspects should be covered:

- Successful business cases of Innovation procurement
- How to define the PPI Awarding Criteria
- Contract management of PCP and PPI
- How to secure the rules of IPR in Innovation procurement

- How to draw Invitation to tender documentation for PCP/PPI
- Open standards vs. lock-in problems in LEA domain
- Check-lists for PCP and PPI projects
- How to build a business case for innovation procurement

6. APPENDIXES

Appendix 1-6

Please find below the following link to get access to the presentations:

<https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/resources/media/>

1. Understanding Innovation Procurement - Instruments and definitions
2. Steps for PPI preparation - Open Market consultation
3. Steps for PPI preparation – Needs assessment and description workshop
4. Understanding the legal framework - How to manage the PCP-PPI link and Coordinated versus Joint procurement actions
5. Steps for PPI preparation - Short presentation of Success business cases
6. Steps for PPI preparation – How to define awarding criteria

